

ISSN 1597 — 8540

**Journal of Applied
Education
And
Vocational Research**

Volume 11 /Number 1/October 2013.

Official Journal of the College of Applied Education and
Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education,
Ijebu-Ode, Nigeria.

EDITORIAL - BOARD

Editor-in-Chief

Professor Niyi Benedict

Dept. of Educational Foundation &
Instructional Technology,
TASUED.

Managing Editor

Dr. F.R. Sulaiman

Edu. Foundation & instructions,
TASLTED.

Associate Editors

Dr. J.T.. Oluwatimilehin

Counselling Psychology Dept.
TASUED.

Dr. M.E. Hassan

Counsding Psychology Dept.
TASUED.

Publishing Journal Secretary

Dr. B.O.O1anisimi

Counselling Psychology, Dept.
TASUEL

Editors:

Dr. K. ijaduola

Dr. Olusonojo

Dr. J.C. Olusanya

Mr. Oduniarni

Consulting Editors:

Professor P.O. desemowo

O.OU. Ago-Iwoye

Professor J.B, aAbalola
Educational Management, U.I.
Professor K.A. Alao,
O.A.U., Ile-Ife
Dr. S.B. Adejuyigbe
FUTA, Akure
Professor Ayo Dada
Teacher Edu. U.I.

JOURNAL OF APPLIED EDUCATION AND VOCATIONAL RESEARCH

Volume 11/Number 1/October 2023

Notes on Contributors

1. Dr. Sarah Sopekan writes from the Faculty of Education, University of Lagos, Lagos, Nigeria.
2. 'Niran Adetoro PhD writes from Department of Edimcatiàna). Management, Library and Information Science Unit, Tai Solarin University of Education, ijebu-Ode.
3. Olatunji O. Fadairo, J.A. Bakare & A.O. Oyenuga write from Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-Ode.
4. Uko-Aviomoh, E.E. Eko, M.E., Akano, R.A. and OiadOymho,. CA. write from Vocational and Technical Education Dejrtment, Tai Solariri University of Education, ijebu-Odé.
5. Onabamiro; AA. Ph.D., Anatasui, Tina & Okon Abigal, Ph.D writ from Tai Solarin University of Education., Ijebu-Ode and Babcock University Ilisan, Nigeria.
6. O.A. Oyebanjo and E.O Joshua write from Ti Solariri University of Education Ijagun IjebuOde and University of Ibadan, Ibadan respectively.
7. Shogunle, O.O. Adewoga, T.O. and Jakkari R.M. write from the College of Science and Information Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode.
8. Peleyeju, J.O. Ph.D. writes from the College of Applied Education and Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode.
9. Dr. J.O. Ogunbiyi, Ph.D writes from the College of Social and Management Sciences, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode.

10. Dr. James Timothy writes from the School of Education, National Open University, Lagos, Nigeria.

11. Odunlami, I.A. Ph.D writes from College of Applied and Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode.

12. Lemo, O.O. Ph.D writes from College of Applied and Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode,

13. Oso S. Oluwatuambi writes from the Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti

14. Ositope, A., Osiyemi, A.J. and Muyiwa Y Adeomi Ph.D. from Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-Ode and Oibisi Onabanjo University Ago-Iwoye respectively.

15. Osunrinde, A.A. writes from the Main Library, Ekiti State University Ado-Ekiti.

16. Olatoye, A.O. writes from the College of Applied & Education and Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode.

17. Oguniokun MO. Ph.D writes from the Faculty of Education University of Ibadan.

18. Dr. Rosemary Ogbodo Abo Ph.D' write from. International of Journalism, Abija. N:gra.

CONTENTS

Pages

Efficacy of Problem Solving Strategy In The Fostering Creativity Skill Among Pre-School Teachers In Lagos Metropolis Dr. Sarah Sopekan

Capacity Building for Sustainable Library and Information Services Development in Nigeria 28-36 'Nircm Adetoro PhD

Work Skills Improvement Needs of Graduates of Technical colleges In Electrical Installation And 7 Maintenance Practice for Employment in The contemporary Nigeria Olatunli Oriola .Fadairo, J. A. Bctkar & OyerLuga, Anthony Oietunde -

Emerging Issues and Risk Management Strategies for food. Security in Nigeria 49

Uko-Aviornoh, E.E., Eko, M.E.; Akano, .R.A., O?adoyinho, C.A.

Analysis of Impediments to Teacher Education And Training. In Nigeria: Implication For National Development Onabarniro, A, Adegbenga, Ph.D, Anatsui, Tina & Okon, Abigael, Ph.D

Radioactivity Levels of Some Rock Samples in Northern Part of Nigeria O.A. Oyebanio, & E.Q Joshua

Students Perception on Gender Related Factors and Academic Performance in Biology: A Case Study of Odogboiu Local Governmeflt Area Shogunle O. O. Adewoga T. O. S., Jakkari R. M.

Lecturers' Performance Appraisal And Total Quality - Management of Public Universities in South-Western Nigeria Peleyeju, Joshua Olusegun Ph.D

Resources and Methods for Improved Social Studies

Teaching In Nursery and Primary Schools in Nigeria 103-114

Dr. Ogunbiyi, .O. (Ph.D.)

A Survey of Nigerian Colleges of Education Biology students' Attitudes towards Wildlife Conservation Dr. James Timothy

Analysis of Effective School Supervision as a Mechanism for Quality Control In Nigerian School³ Odunlami, Idowu Adeniyi Ph.D 134-143

The Impact of Information and Communication technology (ICT) on Vocational and Technical Students' Learning

Lemo Olusiji O.

Effect of classroom management on the academic performance of secondary school students in Ekiti state.]56-174 Oso, Senny Oluwatumbi

The Place of Disabled In Universal Basic Education (UBE) and National Productivity in Nigeria Ositoye Adewale Olorunfemi, Dr "Muyiwa Yemi Adeyerni & Osiyerni A.J

A Christian Librarian in a Corrupt Society Osunrinde, A. A.

The Role of Computer Technology in Effective Teaching and Learning in Business Education Olatoye, A.O.

Psychological Factors as Predictors of Job Performance among Teachers in Iseyin Local Government, Oyo State Moses Oluwafemi Ogundokun, Ph.D

Impact of Boko Haram Terrorism on National Security and Social-Economic Development Dr. Rosemary Ogbodo Abo (Ph.D)

JOURNAL OF APPLIED EDUCATION AN VOCATIONAL RESEARCH

EDITORIAL

The eleven volume, number one - Vol. 11, (1) October, 2013 of .he Journal of Applied Education and Vocational Research is a special edition of the College of Applied Education and Vocational Technology that is poised to report cut-edge research findings and discuss educational issues of interests. The topics of the articles in this issue are contemporary and challenging with their implications or national development and global empowerment.

The editorial board of JAEVR wishes to solicit through this medium well researched studies and articles for future publications. I will like to thank the reviewers and assessors of the articles published, for their time and other' resources well spent. To the contributors the hoard says thank you and please continue to research and send qualitative papers to JAEVR. We solemnly promise a continued improvement in the subsequent publications.

Prof. Niyi Benedict

Editor-m-Chief

Ubom, I. U. (2001). Value orientations, needs satisfaction and job performance of public servants in Akwalbom State. Ph. D. dissertation, University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria.

Ubom, I. U. & Joshua, M. T. (2004). Needs Satisfaction Variables as Predictors of Job Satisfaction of Employees: Implication for Guidance and Counselling Educational Research Journal, 4, 3, 790-801.

Uwaimeiyee, R. & Onyewadunie, M.A (2001). Job satisfaction among teachers in a depressed economy: status, challenges and implications. Nigerian Journal of Applied Psychology, 6, 2, 168-176.

Van der Linde, E. (2005). The relationship between personality traits and work performance of call centre agents. Unpublished master's dissertation, University of South Africa, Pretoria.

Vijay Dhole & Jainiini. (2013). Role of stress and locus of control on job satisfaction among employees with special reference to manufacturing industry. International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research, 2, 1, 93-105.

Viswesvaran, C., Ones, D.S. & Schmidt, F.L. (1996). Comparative analysis of the reliability of job performance ratings. Journal of Applied Psychology, 81, 557-574.

Wade, C. & Tavris, C. (2006). Psychology, (8th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.

Zedeck & Fogil (1988). Interdisciplinary Approaches to Job Design. Journal of Applied Psychology, 73, 3, 457-461.

IMPACT OF BOKO HARAM TERRORISM ON NATIONAL SECURITY AND SOCIAL-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Dr. Rosemary Ogbodo Abo (Ph.D)

International Institute of Journalism, Abuja Camp, Area II

P.O. Box 5914, Area 10, Garki Abuja

E-mail: roseabo@yahoo.com

Tel: 08033158412, 08056205327

Abstract

Terrorism has become a global phenomenon, it is a deliberate and systematic use of violence, to destroy, kill, maim and intimidate the innocent- in order to achieve a goal or draw national and international attention to demands which ordinarily may be impossible or difficult to achieve under normal political negotiation or on the battle field against a government army. Terrorism whether internationalized or localized is always politically motivated, though it may also show other ancillary motives such as religious, economic or social (Obiorn, 2011).

These motives constitute the ideology of a cause for which terrorism seeks solution or sympathy. Terrorism may also arise as a result of a people's historical experience, as consequences of deprivations, war, domination, inequalities, natural and man-made calamities. This paper, therefore examines the incidence of Boko Haram activities, causes, effect on socio-economic development of Nigeria, some of the security measures put in place, and the role of counselors to minimize the incidence.

Introduction

Nigeria has had and still having different terrorist groups such as the Niger Delta Terrorist Groups, Movement for the Survival of Ogoni People (MOSOP), Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Niger Delta People Vokmteer Force, the Ebgesu Boys and Niger Delta Vigilante. According to Obiom (2011), all these groups have a history dating back to Adaka Boro Movement in the 1960's to Ken Saro Wiwa's sfruggles. These groups' agitations are essentially

against environmental degradation, unemployment, poverty, deprivation and marginalization.

In the East the Bakassi Boys, Bakassi Movement for Self Determination, Igbo People's Congress and the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra are all terrorist groups fighting for equal rights and security, true federalism, autonomy and political relevance of their people (Omatala, 2012). The Odua People's Congress (OPC) is the militant wing and mouth piece of Egbe Omo Oduduwa; it is also used by dominant political parties in the west to advance their causes and achieve sanity. The same goes for the Arewa

People's Congress (APC). There are also pockets of other terrorist at the Jos plateau area, among the Igala/Idoma/Zaki Ibiam axis whose interests are mainly rooted in land acquisition, boundary adjustments and grazing rights.

According to Ichedi and Oyetola (2012), Boko Haram is a strong pseudo-Islamic terrorist group which has its base in Kanarrna, in Borno state of Northern Nigeria. The group name, Boko Haram refers to an Islamic sect popularly known for its strong opposition to anything western. The term came from the Hausa word "Boko" which implies western education and the Arabic word "Haram" figuratively means 'sin' and literally forbidden i.e western education is sinful and corrupts Muslim since it is forbidden.

Originally, according to Farouk (2012) the sect adopted its official name from the Arabic term "Jarna'atu Sunna Lidda Await Wat-Jihad" whose English interpretation is 'the group of Al- Sunna for preaching and Jihad or the people committed to the propagation of the prophet's preaching and Jthad' It is opposed to anything that has a western origin such as the western education, ideologies, systems, democracy, etc.

According to John (2011), the group Boko Haram is radically different from all the terrorist groups in Nigeria. It is the most blood — thirsty and destructive both in terms of its demonic brutality, mindless savagery and increasingly scope of operation. A unique feature of this group is suicide bombing, which is quite un-Nigerian. This feature alone has -given them an international standard. –

However, according to Omotola & Momoh (2012), Boko Haram has been in existence since 2001 but became active in 2009 when it participated actively in sectarian violence in Northern Nigeria.

Mohammed Yusuf who remained the leader until he was killed by the Nigeria armed forces, and after his death, Abubakar Shekau became the new Boko Haram leader.

The Boko Haram, its causes and its activities have affected the nation, Nigeria in several aspects and here are some of the security measures put in place that we shall be discussing the counseling implications.

From September, 2009 to December, 2012 there has been massive attacks on the innocent Nigeria citizens ranging from the Bauchi prison break, the Abuja police Headquarters bombing on -June 16th, 2011. The blast on the United Nations building in Abuja on August, 26th, 2011 killed 21 and 60 wounded. Multiple bombings in different locations in the northern parts of the country such as Kano, Kaduna, Jos. Nwosu (2012) posited that churches were not left out too as the various persistent bombings done in catholic churches and other Christian worship centers confirmed this. On December 25th, 2011, January 5th and 6th, 2012 respectively, a catholic church in Madalla around Suleja, Niger State, Mountain of Fire and Miracles, a north — eastern church in Gadaka and some churches in Mubi, Adamawa state and business centers were blasted on Christmas day celebration. This-day newspapers Headquarters in Abuja was also blasted on the 26th, April, 2012. There were attacks on Deeper Life Church in Okene, and Lokoja Kogi state, etc.

In the wake of all these disasters and anarchy in the country a lot of lives have been lost, properties destroyed people psychologically traumatized, public buildings and a lot uncountable losses were recorded

Effects of Boko Haram on Socio-Economic Development of N Nigeria The activities off Boko Haram have negative effects on the socio- economic development of Nigeria in several aspects, namely, social, economic, political security, religious, etc.

Economic Effect: A world investment report of the United Nations conference on Trade and Development estimated that the domestic economy has so far lost a whopping N1.33 trillion. The FDI (Nigeria Foreign Direct Investments) in concurring to the UN report added that the figure given is a small calculation in term of monetary terms (Obiom, 2011). At present, no serious, foreign or local, investor would risk his life or money by investing in the country particularly in the north and this is dragging the economy down the drain.

Kano, a once vibrant commercial nerve centre of the north, serving neighboring countries like Niger, Chad, and Northern Cameroon is nearly desolate; the attacks have scared away customers; in effects, the cost of food crops coming from the north is quite high because very few traders are willing to travel to these troubled zones. In effect, economic development is held down in the north, causing incalculable damage to the nation's economy. The Tourism sector is not left out in the menace. According to Olusegun, (2012); the sector used to generate approximately N80 billion annually but currently this is being disrupted by the suicide bombers.

The aviation industry is not an exception; there has been a drastic reduction of passengers flying to the Northern parts of the country. This is same with the local transporters they have little or no patronage for customers traveling to the far north (Olusegun, 2012).

There is also a huge rise in the number of internally displaced persons especially southerners fleeing from the north. Currently, studies have it that, over 1.7million Nigeria citizens have relocated from Maiduguri to other parts of the country. The effect of such unplanned movement tripled the cost of living in other parts of the country; value of houses went up, causing a lot of hardship to the generality of the masses (Olusegun, 2012).

Security Effect: In the wake of increasing rate of insecurity caused by the Boko Haram, individuals, corporate organizations as well as all levels of government are devoting a large chunk of their budgets to security which they could have used for other organizational and national development at large. In most states in the north and the FCT,

Abuja many churches, beer parlours, mosques, eateries, banks, government secretariats, agencies and embassies amongst others are paying heavily to retain the services of security agents (Adeyi, 2012).

The Boko Haram group has further exposed the weakness and fragility of our internal security system, in terms of poor equipment, poor training, especially in intelligence and adequate personnel and corruption in Nigeria. It has been observed that there exist high level of mistrust among the agencies' rank and files where the junior staffs have little or no confidence in their bosses and visa-vis. The effect is that the civilians doubt and lose confidence in the leadership capability of the government. This perception whether true or false has a negative impact on those who see the police as their defender.

The activities of Boko Haram have also effected foreign direct investment into Nigeria as investors were scared by the level of violence in Nigeria. It is an accepted axiom all over the world that investment is indirectly related to the level of security in a country, that is, the higher the level of violence, the lower the investment.

The Boko Haram activities have diverted government attention from the traditional role of governance as enshrined in the constitution to maintenance of security to tackle the challenges of the radical Islamic sect. A lot of financial resources were allocated to the security sector to the detriment of other sectors.

Religious Effect: Nigeria as a nation had always existed with three major religions - the Christian, Islamic and the Traditional African religions. These religions have existed over the years with respect and regard for one another's belief without interference and interjections but over the last few decades the story has changed especially in the wake of Boko Haram and its massive assaults on the churches. The bombing activities of this sect have created a lot of had blood in the hearts and minds of the victim's families. Their activities have also affected the Christians in the north, they now fear to worship God in churches on Sundays. Their assaults on Christian worshipper have equally forced some worshippers to backslide, and this is a breach of human right to freedom of worship as enshrined in our constitution (Ichdi and Oyetola, 2012).

Another negative effect of Boko Haram activities is social disharmony among the diverse ethnic and cultural groups in Nigeria. For example, in some parts of Northern Nigeria, some religious groups prefer to live in the same environment because of the fear of being attacked by other religious groups. Social disharmony has also led to reduction in inter religious and inter-ethnic marriages previously practiced in the country, and thereby reversing the gains of integration effort by the government since independence (Omotola and Momoh, 2012). Nigerians on legitimate trips abroad are constantly harassed by countries of destination, especially western countries, for being suspected as members of Boko Haram. This is expected to increase if the Boko Haram is declared by the United States government as terrorist group as currently proposed by that country.

Causes of Boko Haram:

Poverty:

Adeyi (2012) quoted the National Bureau of Statistics (2012) to have reported that the Nigerian poverty index was not encouraging; and a lot of people have attributed the cause of Boko Haram to high level of poverty in the country. Poverty is defined as the inability of a person to meet his basic needs of housing, clothing and food. This view is supported by poverty figures recently released by the National Bureau of statistics (NBS) early this year. The report shows that 54% of Nigerians were poor in 2004. The figure rose 69% by 2010. The report estimated that the level of poverty figure will rise to 71.5% in 2011. Please see table one below for more details.

Table 1: Relative poverty Headcount from 1980 -2010

Year	Poverty Incidence (%)	Estimated Population (Million)	Population in Poverty (Million)
1980	27.2	65	17.1
1985	46.3	75	34.7
1992	42.7	91.5	39.2
1996	65.6	102.3	67.1
2004	54.4	126.3	68.7
2010	69.0	163	112.47

Source: National Bureau of Statistics, HNLSS, 2011

The poverty figure when disaggregated shows that the North West has the highest poverty rate of 77%, followed by North East (76%) and North Central (67.5%). In the Southern Nigeria, the South East has the highest poverty rate of 67.0%, followed by South- South respectively. (See table two below for more details).

Table 2: Zonal incidence of poverty, 2010

Zone	Relative poor
North Central	65.5
North East	76.3
North West	77.7
South East	6.70
South-South	63.8
South West	591

From the above statistics, it can be concluded that poverty is pervasive and wide spread in Nigeria. The army of poor Nigerians could be recruited for nefarious activities. No wonder, it did not take time for the founder of Boko Haram sect to recruit multitude of followers to follow his philosophy in Nigeria, especially the North East.

ii. Unemployment: Connected to poverty is the issue of high unemployment rate in Nigeria. Since poverty measurement is based on expenditure, those who are unemployed are automatically referred to as poor. The unemployed are easily tempted to steal, join thugery, armed robbery and other vices. In its 2011 Annual Socio Economic report, the National Bureau of statistics said that 23.9% of Nigerians were unemployed in 2011.

The Urban unemployment rate stood at 25.6% while that of rural is 17.1%. When presented by state, Bauchi state has the highest poverty rate of 41.4%, while Abia has the least rate of 11.2%. The Youths (15-24 years) have the highest unemployment rate of 37.7% compared to other age groups of the population. This may probably be the reason for youth restiveness in some parts of the sectors of the economy. Again see tables 3, 4 and 5 for more details.

SECTOR	RATE
Urban	17.1

Rural	25.6
National	223.9

Table 3: Unemployment Rate by Place of Residence (2011)

National Bureau of Statistics Household Survey, 2011

State	Rate
Abia	11.2
Adamawa	33.8
Akwa Ibom	18.4
Anambra	12.2
Bauchi	41.2
Bayelsa	23.9
Benue	14.2
Borno	29.1
Cross River	18.2
Delta	27.2
Ebonyi	23.1
Edo	35.2
Ekiti	12.1
Enugu	25.2
Gombe	38.7
Imo	26.1
Jigawa	35.9
Kaduna	30.3
Kano	21.3
Katsina	28.1
Kebbi	25.1
Kogi	14.4
Kwara	7.1
Lagos	8.3
Nasarawa	36.5
Niger	39.4
Ogun	22.9
Ondo	12.5
Osun	3.0
Oyo	8.9
Plateau	25.3
Rivers	25.5

Sokoto	17.9
Taraba	12.7
Yobe	35.6
Zamfara	42.6
FCT Abuja	21.1
National	23.9

Table 4, Unemployment Rate by State and Sector (2011)

Table 5: Unemployment Rate by Educational Level, Age-group, sex sector (2011)

National Bureau of Statistics, general Household Survey, 2011

iii. Corruption: This is dishonest or illegal behaviour, especially by people in authority. In Nigeria, corruption has led to people in authority to enrich themselves without working for it. In addition to this primitive accumulation, corruption has made it almost impossible for the right people to be in right positions in the society. This has led to meritocracy in the society in addition to high level of contempt of the poor against the rich causing social disharmony in the society.

iv. Non-functional Education: Education is said to be functional when upon completion of education the graduate is gainfully employed. Unfortunately, most graduates are unemployable because of bad educational system or over production of graduates in certain area of education to the detriment of others Nwosu (2012). For example in Nigeria, more students graduate in social sciences compared to sciences and technical courses.

v. Preaching of Religious Hate: It has been revealed that some religious preachers were found to preach against other religions to their followers instead of preaching the tenets of their religions. Preaching of religious hate had made adherents of such religions to hate those who do not belong to their religious groups. This must stop if there is going to be religious harmony in Nigeria.

vi. Erosion of Cultural Values: The culture of integrity, love of neighbours, service to motherland, etc., have been eroded in the Nigerian Society. The popular idea now is how to make money irrespective of the method it is gotten. The youths are

no longer looking up to the elders for inspiration and guidance because they themselves cannot be trusted. If this trend is not checked by deliberate actions, more crises of Boko Haram are expected in the country.

vi. Lack of Leadership foresight and Intellectual Perversion: In his contribution in a public lecture held at Lagos State Assembly mosque in Ikeja which was published recently, barrister Raheem Ahmed Saji, the Chief Imam of Lekki Central Mosque attributed the problem of Nigeria to “intellectual perversion” by the leadership in addition to their lack of vision. The current security challenges due to Boko Haram activities would have been nipped in the bud from the start if our leaders have vision and foresight. A leader with a vision sees tomorrow today.

Counseling Implications:

Counseling is contributing positively towards behaviour modification. Consequently the Boko Haram are preaching against western education, but counselors can be effective in using various strategies towards counseling the youths against violence in the school setting to prevent the emergence of other violent groups in future.

Counselors should encourage hard work and creativity among the youths to discourage idleness and violence behaviours. This will promote civic education and add value to our society against lawlessness.

Counselors should be employed to work with all tiers of government such as federal, state and local level to counseled against injustices, corruption ethnicity, favoritism, marginalization, etc., and to be transparent at all levels, so as to make the society a better place for citizens to live.

Conclusion

From the above discussion, it is clear that the Boko Haram had caused the country a lot of human and financial resources. The underlying cause of the phenomenon is widely believed to the high level of poverty in Nigeria. Apart from putting security infrastructures to tackle the menace of Boko Haram, government need to come out with policies to prevent the emergence of other violent groups in future.

Based on the above discussion the following recommendations are made to address the problems associated with Boko Haram.

Recommendations:

i. Generation of gainful employment: Government should immediately promote employment generation activities across the country. In the short run, government can embark on direct labour in public works. Secondly government should encourage young Nigerians to go into agriculture for the production of food for the teeming populace and for export by putting the necessary infrastructure in place in the rural areas. In the long run however, government should come up with policies to relieve agriculture of its excess labour to the other sectors of the economy like, manufacturing, construction services, etc.

ii. Empowerment of counselors at all levels of government to carry out research on the youth empowerment so as to make them focused and live purposeful lives. - ii. Modification of the current education curriculum/system: The educational system should focus on production of sound minds that are able to think independently and work with their hands for the socio economic development of the country.

iv. Enactment of law to prohibited preaching of hate in our places of worship: Preaching of religious hate should be discouraged in mosques, churches and other places of worship. Offenders should be given the harshest punishment as deterrent to others. Apart from punishing offenders, the national orientation agency should come out with ways of re-orienting the minds of people against this act.

v. Control of corruption: There should be a zero tolerance to corruption because it is a cankerworm that can destroy the country, Nigeria. The Anti-corruption agencies should be made independent and the heads of these agencies should be persons of unquestionable character.

vi. Strengthening of the National Bureau of Statistics: The National Bureau Statistics should be strengthened to generate credible data for the formulation, implementation and evaluation of policies, planning, and monitoring of development programmes and among others. The saying: "If you cannot measure it, you cannot change it," implied here. We need quality statistical information on

all spheres of our national life to enable us change our current situation for a better future.

Reference

Adeyi, O.V. (2012) Conflict Resolution among our Youths in Six Local Government Area in Otokpo Local Government of Benue State, M.Sc. thesis (unpublished).

Farouk, C. (2012) Who are Nigeria's Boko Haram Islamists? BBC News [http /www.hbcco. uk/news/world Africa 1380950/ /](http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world_Africa_1380950/) retrieved 2012—01-25.

Ichedi, J.E. & Oyetola, S.A (2012) Youths Empowerment, a way out for Boko Haram; Unpublished manual handbook: Abuja.

Johnson, TO (2011) “Backqrounder, Boko Haram” Coancil on Foreign Relation. [Http/www.cfr. org/Africa/Bokoharam/](Http/www.cfr.org/Africa/Bokoharam/) page 25739 Retrieved. 2011 — 09 — 01.

National Bureau of Statistics (2012); Report on Poverty in Nigeria.

Nwosu, V.T (2012) The Role of Mother in our Society: A Presentation for Market Women, Utako Market square, Abuja on 16 August 2012.

Obiom, H.O. (2011) Terrorism and the Future of our Children, what next? Unpublished manual book, Abuja.

Olusegi.m R. (2012) Speech delivered on the International Conference held on Trade/Nigeria Tourism on 18 — 02 — 2012 at International Conference Centre, Abuja. (Unpublished Manual).

Omotola, A.A & Momoh, H. (2012) Terrorism has eaten up deep among Nigerian citizens, help, help, Published in National Mirror of 8th June2012.

Dr Sarah Sopekan writes from the Faculty of Education, University of Lagos, Lagos, Nigeria.

- 'Nfran Adetoro PhD writes from Department of Educational Management,. Library and Information Science Unit, Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-Ode.

- Olaturiji O. Fadaird, J.A. Bakare & A.O. Oyenuga write from Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-Ode.

- Ukà-Aviómoh, E.E. Eko, M.E,Akano, R.A. and Oladoyinbo, C.A write from Vocational and Technical Education Department, Tai Solann University of Education, Ijebu-Ode

- Onabanuiró, A: Ph.D. Anastasui, Tina & Okón Abigal, Ph.D write from Tai Solarift University of Education, Ijebu-Ode and Babcock University Ilisan, Nigeria.

- O.A. Oyebanjo and E.O Joshriawrite from Tai Splarin University oft.

- Education Ijagur Ijebu-Ode and Uniyersityof Ibadan,. Ibadan..

respectively -

- Shogunle, OO, Adewoga, T O and Jakkan R M write from th& College of Science and Information Technology, Tai Solann

University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode..

- Pelèyeju, J.O. Ph.D writes from the College of Applied Education and Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education

Ijaguri Ijebu-Ode.

- Dr. J.O. Ogunbiyi, Ph.D writes from the College of Social and Management Sciences, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun

Ijebu-Ode.

- Dr. James Timothy writes from the School of Education, National Open University, Lagos, Nigeria.

- Odunlami I.A. Ph.D writes from College of Applied and Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode

- Lemo, O.O. Ph.D writes from College of Applied and Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode.

Oso S. Oluwaturimbi writes from the Faculty Of Education, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti. . --.

Ositoye, A , Osiyenii, A J and Muyiwa Y Adeyenu Ph D write from Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-Ode and Olabisi Ohabanjo University Ago-Iwoye respectively.

Osunrinde, A.A. writes from the Main Library, Ekiti State University Ado-Ekiti.

Olatoye, A.O. writes from the College of Applied Education and Vocational Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijagun Ijebu-Ode.

Ogundokun, M.O. Ph.D writes from. the Faculty of Education University of Ibadan. .

Dr. Rosemary Ogbodo Abo (Ph.D) writes from International Institute of Journalism, Abuja, Nigeria.